

Raman Spectroscopy of the Iron Oxides and Hydroxides: a Review

Amelia Carolina Sparavigna

Department of Applied Science and Technology, Polytechnic University of Turin, Italy

Email: amelia.sparavigna@polito.it

Abstract

Magnetic iron oxides, such as Fe_3O_4 , $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, have unique magnetic, catalytic and biochemical features, rendering them suitable for several specific technological and biomedical applications. In a previous study, for instance, we considered the magnetite Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles dispersed in supporting materials to obtain composites that can better respond to electromagnetic interferences with an increased EMI shielding effectiveness. Here we investigate how to distinguish the iron oxide nanoparticles by means of their Raman spectra. We will stress that literature is evidencing a challenge. This challenge is due to the fast transformations of iron oxides when laser power is applied. Therefore, the Raman spectroscopy needs to be considered carefully for determining the nature of the iron oxide present in the investigated samples. The role of oxidation of magnetite will be addressed in detail. In the review, the reader can find the Raman “fingerprints” of some oxides and hydroxides: Magnetite, Maghemite, Hematite, Goethite and Lepidocrocite.

Keywords: Raman spectroscopy, Magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles, Fe_3O_4 , Magnetite, Electromagnetic interference shielding effectiveness, IONPs

Torino, August 31, 2023.

Introduction

In a previous study (Sparavigna, 2023), we considered the iron oxide Fe_3O_4 in the form of nanoparticles (NPs) dispersed in a supporting material, to obtain a composite that can respond to the electromagnetic (EM) fields by absorbing a part of their energy. The use of magnetic NPs aims to improve the EM interference shielding effectiveness (EMI-SE) and, at the same time, to reduce the reflection loss (RL) (Avloni et al., 2007). The iron oxide nanoparticles are sometimes mentioned as being MIONs (Monocrystalline Iron Oxide Nanoparticles) or designed as belonging to the family of IONPs, iron oxide NPs. Because of their superparamagnetic (SPM) behavior, the Fe_3O_4 particles are SPM IONPs or SPIONs (Wallyn et al., 2019). Dispersed in a supporting material, IONPs can respond to an external magnetic field (Tong et al., 2019).

About IONPs, a review was proposed by Wu et al., 2015. The review illustrates the “strategies in the preparation, microstructure, and magnetic properties of bare and surface functionalized” IONPs (Wu et al., 2015). Biological applications are addressed: for instance, magnetic IONPs “as a contrast agent for in vitro diagnostics has been practiced for nearly half a century” (Wu et al. and references therein). More recently, magnetic IONPs has been largely investigated for the targeted drug delivery and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), besides other biological applications (see Wu et al. and references therein). Among the technological applications, we focused on the EMI-SE increase obtained by means of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles, however catalysis is also largely employing them (reviews by Pereira et al., 2012, Pouran et al., 2014, and Kumar et al., 2022).

Wu et al., mentioning Cornell and Schwertmann, 2003, tell that eight iron oxides are known, and that the most popular are hematite ($\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), magnetite (Fe_3O_4) and maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), possessing “polymorphism, involving temperature-induced phase transition”. “Each of these three iron oxides has unique biochemical, magnetic, catalytic, and other properties which provide suitability for specific

technical and biomedical applications” (Wu et al., 2015). Besides oxides, we have oxyhydroxides. “All together, there are sixteen known iron oxides and oxyhydroxides with different mineral structures” (Fernández-Remolar, 2015). The above mentioned Fe_3O_4 (magnetite) is the $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}\text{Fe}_2^{\text{III}}\text{O}_4$ which is containing the divalent form of iron (Fernández-Remolar, 2015).

Having so many oxides, we can ask ourselves if it is possible to distinguish them by means of the Raman spectroscopy. This spectroscopy is named after the Indian physicist Sir Chandrasekhara Venkata Raman. The technique is based on the vibrational modes of molecules, relying upon the inelastic scattering of photons, that is the Raman scattering. A source of monochromatic light, usually a laser, is providing the photons interacting with molecular vibrations, phonons and other excitations. The outgoing inelastically scattered photons have a shifted frequency, which is giving information about the vibrational modes. The elastically scattered photons, which have a wavelength corresponding to the laser line (Rayleigh scattering), are filtered out. The several iron oxides possess different crystal lattices and symmetries, so phonons and other vibrational modes seem being quite distinguishable, and consequently the Raman spectroscopy appears as a method easy to handle.

As stressed by Monika Hanesch, 2009, in her study about the Raman spectroscopy of synthetic and natural iron oxides and (oxy)hydroxides, “most of them can be identified by magnetic methods, but there are some minerals that are not easy to differentiate from each other. In these cases, the magnetic methods can be complemented by Raman spectroscopy” (Hanesch, 2009). However, Raman spectroscopy must be carefully used: “A major challenge is the fast transformation of many iron minerals if laser power is applied, especially if the material is poorly crystallized as often is the case in environmental material” (Hanesch, 2009). Monika Hanesch used very low laser powers. But, even with low powers, “the investigated iron minerals could be distinguished from each other.”

Let us start our review showing some Raman spectra from RRUFF and ROD databases. References to RRUFF and ROD databases are Lafuente et al., 2015, and El Mendili et al., 2019, respectively.

ROD (Raman Open) database

In this database, we can find spectra of Magnetite and Hematite. The iron(II,III) oxide is the chemical compound with formula Fe_3O_4 . The mineral form is the magnetite. The iron(III) oxide (Fe_2O_3) occurs as the mineral hematite.

Fig.1: Raman spectra of Fe_3O_4 (Magnetite, laser 633 nm) and Fe_2O_3 (Hematite, laser 514 nm). Fe_3O_4 (data courtesy Kumar et al., 2019), <https://solsa.crystallography.net/rod/3500283.rod>, Fe_2O_3 (data courtesy El Mendili et al., 2012), <https://solsa.crystallography.net/rod/1000001.rod>

Fig.2: Deconvolution of a part of the Magnetite spectrum obtained by means of q -Gaussian functions. The best fit (green) is onto data (red) provided by Kumar et al., 2019; frequency range is from 153 to 900 cm^{-1} (see Fig.1). For the deconvolution, five q -Gaussians have been used. For the stronger peaks the values of the q -parameters are given in the figure. A quite flat q -Gaussian seems being related to a band at 475 cm^{-1} . In the following discussion of the magnetite Raman spectrum, we will see that a band at 470-472 cm^{-1} has been detected. In the lower part of the plot, the misfit is also proposed. On the right, the same fit is shown with the log scale for y-axis (semi log scale). Data and q -Gaussians are given as functions of integers n (equally spaced points used in fitting), for the x-axis which is representing the Raman shift. A convenient scale is used for the y-axis (intensity axis). The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations.

In the Figure 2, we are also proposing the deconvolution in q -Gaussian (Tsallis) functions of a part of the magnetite spectrum. The parameter q is spanning values from 1 to 2. For $q=2$, the q -Gaussian function is a Lorentzian distribution, for q close to 1, it is the Gaussian. The deconvolution in q -Gaussians of Raman and SERS spectra has been proposed for the first time by me (Sparavigna, 2023).

Raman shift (cm^{-1}), Hematite: 229 (strong) 248 295 414 502 614 1320 (strong)

Raman shift (cm^{-1}), Magnetite: 190.5 301 534 663.5 (strong)

RRUFF database

In RRUFF Project website, searching for **magnetite** ($\text{Fe}^{2+}\text{Fe}^{3+}_2\text{O}_4$), we can find the following Raman spectra (<https://rruff.info/magnetite>): R060191, source Lloyd Twaites, R060222, source Rock Currier, R060656, source Michael Scott, R061111, source Michael Scott, R080025, source William W. Pinch, and R140861, source Rock Currier.

Fig.3a: Raman spectra from RRUFF Project website, R060191, R060222 and R060656 (Magnetite).

In the Figure 3a, the Raman spectra (depolarized) of R060191, measured chemistry $(\text{Fe}^{2+}_{0.97}\text{Mg}_{0.03})(\text{Fe}^{3+}_{0.97}\text{Al}_{0.03})_2\text{O}_4$, R060222 measured chemistry $(\text{Fe}^{2+}_{0.95}\text{Mg}_{0.05})(\text{Fe}^{3+}_{0.99}\text{Al}_{0.01})_2\text{O}_4$ and R060656 measured chemistry $(\text{Fe}^{2+}_{0.98}\text{Mg}_{0.01}\text{Mn}_{0.01})(\text{Fe}^{3+}_{1.96}\text{Ti}_{0.02}\text{Mg}_{0.02})\text{O}_4$ are shown.

Fig.3b: Raman spectrum from RRUFF Project website, R060191, in semi logarithmic scale. About 500 cm^{-1} , the semi log scale is evidencing a possible band (shoulder).

Fig3c: Raman spectra from RRUFF Project website, R061111, R080025 and R140861 (Magnetite).

In the Figure 3c, the Raman spectra (laser 532 nm) of R061111 (according to RRUFF measured chemistry $(\text{Fe}^{2+}_{0.51}\text{Ni}_{0.48}\text{Co}_{0.01})_{\Sigma=1}\text{Fe}^{3+}_2\text{O}_4$; trace amounts of Al), R080025 (no measured chemistry available) and R140861 measured chemistry $(\text{Fe}^{2+}_{0.82}\text{Ni}_{0.18})\text{Fe}^{3+}_{2.00}\text{O}$. Note in the Figure 4, that we have a large presence of impurities, in particular in the third sample R080025.

Let us consider from RRUFF the **hematite samples** too, <https://rruff.info/hematite>, which are R040024 University of Arizona Mineral Museum, X050102 CIT – 2058, R050300 Eugene Schlepp, R060190 Lloyd Twaites, R070240 Michael Scott, and R110013 University of Arizona Mineral Museum.

Fig.4a: Raman spectra from RRUFF Project website, R040024, X050102 and R050300 (Hematite).

Fig.4b: Raman spectra from RRUFF Project website, R060190, R070240 and R110013 (Hematite).

In the Figure 4a we can see the Raman spectra from RRUFF Project website, R040024 ($\text{Fe}_{1.99}\text{Al}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$) depolarized, X050102 no chemistry data available, laser 785 nm, and R050300 $\text{Fe}_{2.00}\text{O}_3$. In the Figure 4b, we find R060190 laser 532nm, R070240 $\text{Fe}_{2.00}\text{O}_3$ laser 532nm, and R110013 Fe_2O_3 532 nm.

Fig.5: Raman spectrum R040024 (hematite) and positions of peaks.

Raman shift (cm^{-1}), Hematite:

119 225 246.5 296.5 411 (strong) 500 558 610.5 659.5 1319 (strong)

Magnetite and laser-induced thermal effects and oxidation

Let us consider the article entitled “Raman study of magnetite (Fe_3O_4): laser-induced thermal effects and oxidation”, by Shebanova and Lazor, 2003. In it, we can find a study of natural magnetite (single crystal and powder) with the Raman spectroscopy at different laser powers. The laser power, if enough high, is inducing the oxidation of the sample. “In the course of the oxidation of the single crystal of magnetite, the first characteristic features of hematite appear at about 300 and 410 cm^{-1} , at a temperature close to 240 °C. This may explain the *erroneous assignment* of these modes to the intrinsic Raman modes of magnetite in some studies” (Shebanova & Lazor, 2003). In the case of a finely powdered magnetite, we have a material which is “much more easily prone to oxidation”. During the reaction mechanism, we find the “metastable maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) before the final product hematite is formed”.

Mentioning De Faria et al., 1997, Shebanova and Lazor stress that “the high density of power from a laser excitation source often poses a problem in a Raman experiment owing to its adverse effects on a sample”. In the case of micro-Raman experiments, where the laser beam is focused to a spot of a few micrometers in diameter, the spot temperature can increase even by hundreds of degrees. Consequently, the shift of Raman modes changes. But we can have also “the alteration of a sample as the result of effects such as oxidation, recrystallization, order–disorder transitions (cation redistribution), phase transition or decomposition” (Shebanova & Lazor, 2003). The iron oxides are “good absorbers” of laser radiation, and therefore “belong to materials where *care has to be taken* when conducting a Raman experiment”. Moreover, magnetite is easily oxidized at elevated temperatures, when measurements are made “in open air containing moisture” (Shebanova & Lazor, 2003).

In the Figure 2 of the article by Shebanova and Lazor we can see Raman spectra of a single crystal of magnetite, obtained in the case of a stepwise increase in laser power. As in the case of our Figure 1, for the laser power of 10 mW, we can observe the peaks at 190.5 (very weak), 301 (weak), 534 and 663.5 (strong) (cm^{-1}). “New features in the spectra begin to appear when the power is increased above 20 mW. ... Concurrently, the intensities of the Raman bands of magnetite gradually vanish. Analysis of the spectrum of the final reaction product shows that magnetite, subjected to increased laser power in the course of the Raman experiment conducted in air, was oxidized to the trivalent iron oxide hematite ($\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$)” (Shebanova & Lazor, 2003).

Shebanova and Lazor made also experiments on fine-grained powder of magnetite. The increase of laser power is producing effects on Raman spectrum attributed to oxidation. “Broadening and a deterioration of bands in the 400–600 cm^{-1} region, along with the development of a new peak at about 700 cm^{-1} , indicate the first stage of the oxidation of magnetite ... The presence of hematite bands in the spectrum, along with those of maghemite, is explained by the *metastability of maghemite* with respect to hematite. The Raman spectra collected at higher powers are consistent with pure hematite” (Shebanova & Lazor, 2003).

Magnetite Raman shift frequencies

In the article entitled “Raman spectroscopic study of magnetite (FeFe_2O_4): a new assignment for the vibrational spectrum”, by the same authors, Shebanova and Lazor, 2003, we can find an overview of Raman frequencies available from different studies. The following Raman shift frequencies are given in cm^{-1} .

Verble (1974), at 77K:	300	320	420		560	680		
Boucherit et al. (1991):					550	670		
Hart et al. (1976):	298	320	420	472	550	676		
Dünnwald and Otto (1989):	298	319	418	470	550	676	1322	
Ohtsuka et al. (1986):					540	665		
Thierry et al. (1991):					550	670		
De Faria et al. (1997):		301.6			533.6	662.7		
Gasparov et al. (2000):	193	308			540	670		
Degiorgi et al. (1987) at 130K:	160		318	410	462	542	672	
Graves et al. (1988):	226		336		490	570	706	
Li et al. (2000):		311			540	665		
Bersani et al. (1999):		311			541	666		
Murugappan et al. (2014):		311	360		488		677	
Gupta et al. (2002):		300		410		540	669	
Shebanova and Lazor (2003):	193	306				538	668	
Kumar et al. (2018):	190.5	301				534	663.5	
Thibeau et al. (1978):						616	663	
Mohammed et al. (2018):	272	319	362			543	616	668
Legodi & de Waal (2007):		297				523	666	
Chamritski & Burns (2005):	193	308				540	670	

Some of these data have been previously proposed by De Faria et al. To the data from Table 2 of Shebanova and Lazor (2003) we added those by Kumar et al., 2018 and Murugappan et al., 2014. Also Mohammed et al., 2018, have provided data. The Raman spectroscopic analysis for magnetite is shown in their Table 1 and Figure 2; “the presence of the characteristic bands of magnetite Raman bands occurring at 272, 319, 543 and 668 cm^{-1} are consistent with references”. The works mentioned by Mohammed and coworkers are those by Legodi and de Waal, 2007, Shebanova and Lazor, 2003, and Chamritski and Burns, 2005; we have considered the given references and found slightly different values of the positions of the peaks. Mohammed and coworkers add that “Bands of other material are noticed, peaks observed at 702 cm^{-1} provide evidence due to the presence of hematite in agreement of mentioned in the literatures [Thibeau et al.], also bands at 458, 511, 591 and 764 cm^{-1} and assigned to silicate,” and we can find also other compounds (see references in Mohammed et al.).

In the article by Shebanova and Lazor it is told that “some studies report two additional Raman bands at around 300 and 410–420 cm^{-1} ”. The researchers “note that these lines belong to the characteristic features of spectrum of hematite representing the $E_g(3)$ and $E_g(4)$ modes, respectively” (the reference mentioned is Beattie and Gilson, 1970). The reason is the *bivalent iron* which “makes magnetite easily prone to oxidation”.

In De Faria et al., we find told that some of the reported magnetite peak positions (Hart et al., Verble, and Dünnwald and Otto) “are suspiciously close to the values expected for hematite. Thibeau et al. reported the Raman spectrum of a mixture of 90% Fe_3O_4 and 10% $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ by weight and the coincidence of this spectrum with that reported by Dünnwald and Otto is evident” (De Faria et al., 1997). The peak at 1322 cm^{-1} , “assigned to a hematite two-magnon scattering, is not a feature expected

in a magnetite spectrum, reinforcing the assumption that hematite is present as a contaminant” (De Faria et al. 1997).

In the Figure 3(a) of De Faria et al., we can find the Raman spectrum “of a freshly fractured crystal face at room temperature”, and “only the bands at 300, 532 and 661 cm^{-1} are observed”. However, the laser power is affecting the sample; “when the laser power is raised to 7 mW new bands show up”. Comparison to the spectrum of hematite, De Fria and coworkers conclude that hematite is formed and that “the spectral *changes are irreversible*”. “Transformation of magnetite into hematite is a very common phenomenon in nature and is called *martitization*” (De Faria et al.).

As noted by De Faria and coworkers, in Hart et al. (1976), it is possible to find a very weak feature at 472 cm^{-1} , feature assigned to magnon scattering and in agreement with neutron data. Let us consider again our Figure 2, where the deconvolution with q-gaussians is given. A band at 475 cm^{-1} is present.

To approach the study of the iron oxide Raman spectra, ROD and RRUFF databases are perfect to properly visualize them. A Google search for images is, at the same time, intriguing and can help us to add further information. Plots which appear are very attractive. The first three images appearing in the search are from Hai et al., 2008, Yew et al., 2017, and Panta and Bergmann, 2015. Let us start considering the second reference.

Other data about magnetite nanoparticles and films

In Yew et al., 2017, we can find proposed the Raman spectrum of magnetite nanoparticles (Fe_3O_4 -NPs). In the Figure 7 by Yew et al. we can see shown the spectra of *K. alvarezii*(seaweed)/ Fe_3O_4 -NPs (coated NPs) and bare Fe_3O_4 -NPs, and it is told that “both of the spectra show similar pattern”. From the Figure, we can obtain the Raman shift of the peaks (coated and bare NPs), given at (cm^{-1}):

Coated	212	272	388	474	585	1277
Bare	216	282	396	489	596	1294

The authors say that the peak at 1294 cm^{-1} is the D-band: “This might be due to the presence of defects at the surface of NPs” (mentioning Mishra and Ramaprabhu, 2011). “The characteristic bands for Fe_3O_4 are located at approximately 670, 538 and 306 cm^{-1} (mentioning Murugappan et al., 2014). That is:

Murugappan et al.	306	538	670
-------------------	-----	-----	-----

Murugappan et al. data agree with the previously given data (Murugappan and coworkers do not provide information about laser equipment). But in the Figure 7 of Yew et al., we do not have these values. Yew and coworkers continue: “However, there are 3 peaks can be observed at around 388, 474 and 585 cm^{-1} [values for coated NPs], which corresponded to the vibration modes of Fe-O bonds of Fe_3O_4 -NPs” (mentioning Mishra and Ramaprabhu, 2011). Let us stress that the positions of the peaks, for coated and bare NPs given by Yew and coworkers, are far from the positions given by Murugappan et al., 2014, and by the literature that we have previously mentioned. However, Yew et al. conclude that “Raman spectrum can be found from literature [mentioning Murugappan et al., 2014] and thus the formation of Fe_3O_4 -NPs is confirmed. The peaks at 212 and 274 cm^{-1} are due to the oxidation reaction occurred during Raman experiment” (Yew et al. mentioning Yuvakkumar and Hong, 2014). Yew and coworkers confirmed the presence of Fe_3O_4 NPs with positions of peaks which are different from those of the

typical fingerprint of magnetite. Therefore, it is strictly necessary to consider in depth the articles mentioned by Yew et al.

Mishra and Ramaprabhu, 2011, do not give information about the Fe₃O₄ NPs that they use to decorate multiwalled carbon nanotubes. In their Figure 5, the researchers show the Raman spectra of functionalized MWNTs and Fe₃O₄-MWNT nanocomposite. We find the peaks of Fe₃O₄-MWNTs at:

225.2 285.2 394.8 591.4 1336.4 1565.8

(in cm⁻¹). “Raman spectroscopic analysis of the f-MWNTs shows a comparable intensity of the D-band ..., [the D-band] is due to the presence of more defects at the surface of the MWNTs due to functionalization” (Mishra and Ramaprabhu, 2011). Defects are at the surface of nanotubes, not at the surface of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles. Besides the D and G bands of nanotubes, we can find extra bands. “These extra peaks arise due to the formation of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles over the surface of the MWNTs. Peaks at lower Raman shift (225.2, 285.2, 394.8 and 591.4 cm⁻¹) values may correspond to vibration modes of Fe–O bonds of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles and Fe–C bonds at the surface of the MWNTs” (Mishra and Ramaprabhu are mentioning Tiwari et al., 2008, 2007). Then, let us consider these references.

In Tiwari et al., 2008, we can find Fe₃O₄ thin films. “Raman scattering was performed at room temperature to investigate the effect of substrate [no carbon substrates at all!] and thickness on the vibrational properties. The presence of various modes in Fe₃O₄ can be found in [Gasparov et al., 2000]. Figure 2 shows the Raman spectra of all the Fe₃O₄ films. [Tiwari et al.] observe three modes:” and these modes are about 310, 540 and 670 cm⁻¹. In Tiwari et al., 2007, in the Figure 3 the Raman spectra of Fe₃O₄ films on different substrates are given and again we find peaks about 540 and 670 cm⁻¹. In Tiwari et al., carbon is not present or mentioned (see more details in the Appendix about Tiwari et al. works).

Yew et al. are telling that “Raman spectrum can be found from literature”, mentioning Murugappan et al., 2014. Murugappan and coworkers are providing data about synthesized Fe₃O₄ NPs with oleic acid as surfactant. “Raman spectroscopy was performed to “fingerprint” the vibrational and rotational bands that are specific to Fe₃O₄. Several Raman spectroscopic studies [see footnote¹] of Fe₃O₄ have been performed, and the characteristic bands for Fe₃O₄ are located at approximately 670, 538, and 306 cm⁻¹”. In the Figure 2 of the article by Murugappan and coworkers the Raman spectrum of the synthesized Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles has been proposed with the spectra of magnetite and hematite. “It can be seen that the spectrum of the *synthesized Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles closely resembles that of the pure magnetite* sample. The absence of bands at 205 and 268 cm⁻¹ further indicated that the synthesized material was indeed Fe₃O₄ and not Fe₂O₃”. The “Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles are susceptible to oxidation, which would result in a loss of magnetization. The spectrum suggested that the synthesized nanoparticles were not oxidized” (Murugappan et al., 2014). In Sparavigna, 2023, when discussing the Fe₃O₄ iron oxide for improving EMI-SE, I have encountered a lot of encapsulated Fe₃O₄ NPs; encapsulation is preventing oxidation, such as their coating (Bruschi & de Toledo, 2019, Aisida et al., 2020).

Here the data from Murugappan and coworkers (in cm⁻¹):

<i>Hematite:</i>	205	268	328		560
<i>Magnetite:</i>		311	360	488	677
<i>Magnetite NPs:</i>		314	364	500	679

¹) Murugappan and coworkers are mentioning Shebanova and Lazor, 2003, Verble, 1974, De Faria et al., 1997, Gasparov et al., 2000, Graves et al., 1988.

Let us also consider the article by Yuvakkumar and Hong. In the Figure 1b of their article we can see the Raman spectrum of green synthesized Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles (to synthesize the particles the rambutan peel waste extract has been used as a green ligation and chelating agent). In fact, no specific data about the Raman shift are given in their figure. It is told that “The characteristic bands at 670 and 318 cm^{-1} were attributed to the Fe-O normal vibrations of magnetite Fe_3O_4 The peaks at 300 and $410\text{--}420\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were relevant to an oxidation reaction during a Raman experiment. The bands at 538 (T_{2g}), 306 (E_g) and 194 cm^{-1} (T_{2g}) were characteristics of magnetite Fe_3O_4 [Venkateswarlu et al., 2014]. The result proves that the synthesized iron oxide is Fe_3O_4 ” (Yuvakkumar and Hong).

What is the iron oxide in Yew et al.? It does not possess the fingerprint of magnetite. The same for the iron oxide by Mishra and Ramaprabhu. Is it enough to observe two peaks of oxidation to conclude the presence of magnetite?

Superparamagnetism

Before discussing the role of the laser power in the measurements by Yew and coworkers, let us introduce the magnetism in Fe_3O_4 NPs. In Blaney, 2007, we can find the detailed description of magnetite (Fe_3O_4). A section of the article explores the bulk properties of it. Referring to Cornell and Schwertmann, 1996, Lee Blaney is evidencing a semi-conductor behavior, bordering the conductor (metallic) behavior, of the magnetite. A semimetallic behavior of magnetite is also supported by the relatively low bandgap (0.1 eV) of the material (Cornell & Schwertmann, 1996). The Curie temperature is at 850 K . Below the Curie temperature, we can find the magnetite as a ferrimagnetic material (Cornell & Schwertmann, 1996). “When the Curie temperature is attained, a superparamagnetic behavior is observed”. 850 K is the Curie temperature of the bulk material. If we consider the particles, as the particle size decreases, the behavior tends towards a paramagnetic or superparamagnetic magnetization. Therefore, the decreasing of the particle size reduces ferrimagnetic behavior and enhances superparamagnetic behavior (Blaney, 2007).

The bulk magnetite is ferrimagnetic, “generated by parallel alignment of magnetic moments on tetrahedral sites and anti-parallel alignment of ferrous and ferric spins on octahedral sites” (Blaney, 2007). In the Figure 10 by Blaney, we can see a generic ferrimagnetic hysteresis loop, with indicated coercivity and remanence (retentivity), “As particle size is decreased, the amount of exchange-coupled spins resisting spontaneous magnetic reorientation is decreased, tending towards paramagnetic or superparamagnetic magnetization” (Blaney, 2007, mentioning Kiely, 2006). When the magnetite particle size decreases, the ferrimagnetic behavior is reduced and the superparamagnetic behavior enhanced. Increasing the temperature, the thermal energy facilitates “magnetic reorientation, or superparamagnetic magnetization” (Blaney mentioning Kiely). “In accordance with superparamagnetic behavior, magnetite nanoparticles exhibit zero coercivity and remanence in hysteresis loops as illustrated in Figure 11 [of Blaney, 2007]. Coercivity slowly builds as magnetite particle diameter increases”. In the caption of the mentioned figure, it is told that the absence of hysteresis loop is implying superparamagnetism (Hou et al., 2003).

The image shows the magnetization versus the applied field ($M\text{--}H$) for superparamagnetic (SPM) (green color) and ferrimagnetic (FM) (orange) Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles. Image courtesy Nguyen et al., 2021, article distributed under <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

“The superparamagnetic (SPM) and ferrimagnetic (FM) behaviors of Fe₃O₄ NPs depend on size, shape, crystallinity, and surface properties and are even affected by synthetic methods” (Nguyen et al., 2021, and references therein).

In the Figure 8 by Yew et al., we can find the magnetization curves of K. alvarezii/Fe₃O₄-NPs and bare Fe₃O₄-NPs at room temperature. In both curves, the hysteresis is absent and therefore the nanoparticles produced by Yew and coworkers are displaying a superparamagnetic behavior. Superparamagnetism is observed in the Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles (Blaney, 2007; for the properties of bulk iron oxides, see please the Appendix).

Laser power (debris fingerprint)

In Slavov et al., 2010, we can find the Raman spectroscopy used to investigate the magnetite nanoparticles dispersed in two types of β-cyclodextrin suspensions. “The effect of elevating laser power on the structural stability and chemical composition of magnetite in the ferrofluids is discussed. ... Powder samples undergo total phase transition from magnetite to hematite at laser power of 1.95 mW. ... The Raman spectra revealed that the main phase of the magnetic [particle] core ... is magnetite. That is indicated by a strong and non-diminishing in intensity peak at 670 cm⁻¹” (Slavov et al., 2010). “A second phase is present at the nanoparticle’s surface with Raman spectroscopy unveiling *maghemite-like and small fractions of goethite-like structures*” (Slavov et al., 2010).

Slavov and coworkers tested the magnetite by increasing the laser power from 0.9 to 9.0 mW. “The characteristic peak positions of magnetite (Fe₃O₄) and its possible oxidation byproducts, maghemite (γ-Fe₂O₃) and hematite (α-Fe₂O₃) *determined the Raman region of interest*” in Slavov et al. investigation. The range is 100–1200 cm⁻¹. “For correct assignment of the band positions ... and for phase identification,” Vlasov and coworkers used the following peaks (in cm⁻¹): Magnetite 193 (weak), 306 (weak), 538 (weak), 668 (strong); Maghemite 350 (strong), 500 (strong), 700 (strong); Hematite 225 (strong), 247 (weak), 299 (strong), 412 (strong), 497 (weak), 613 (medium).

“The analysis of all spectra reveals the destructive influence of the atmospheric oxygen on the structural stability of even coated magnetite nanoparticles. *For the uncoated magnetite particles, a timeline of less than 30 days meant a total transition towards maghemite. ... The oxidation process starts at a very early stage after formation of the nanoparticles*” (Slavov et al., 2010).

In the Figure 3 of the article by Slavov and coworkers, we can see the Raman spectra of powdered magnetite nanoparticles obtained with a laser power of 0.060 mW and a laser power of 1.95 mW. The peaks are (in cm⁻¹):

0.060 mW:		383	463	519	670	
1.95 mW:	215	276	386		584	1280

Here we are ready to consider again the data from Yew et al., 2017, about bare and coated nanoparticles.

Coated NPs:	212	272	388	474	585	1277
Bare NPs:	216	282	396	489	596	1294

We can tell that we are observing the debris fingerprint of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles, because the laser power was enough high to cancel the typical peaks of magnetite. The Fe₃O₄ particles prepared by Yew and coworkers are superparamagnetic. Let us stress that hematite can have a superparamagnetic behavior too. “For hematite in the nanoparticle morphology, [the bulk] characteristics are affected by the particle

size and shape. Spherical particles with diameter smaller than 25–30 nm are superparamagnetic and the Morin temperature is lowered significantly or even suppressed” (see Lee et al., 2014, and references therein). Yew et al. definitely concluded about magnetite thanks to the XRD analysis (see please the Figure 3 in their article, comparing with the following figure).

XRD data for Magnetite and Hematite (in the lower panel, in black data of magnetite and in red of hematite). Data from RRUFF, <https://rruff.info/magnetite/display=default/R060191> and <https://rruff.info/hematite/display=default/R040024>.

About the laser power, let us add what we can find in Panta and Bergmann, 2015: “it is known that magnetite has a weak Raman scattering, especially for lower laser powers”. Increasing the laser power induces phase transformations. Besides the influence of power, Panta and Bergmann note that also the wavelength is relevant:

Laser 512 nm: 215 276 398 487 654 1300

Laser 785 nm: 670

into hematite”, the study is made with different “laser power and exposure to oxygen. Under hematite-free conditions, the Raman data indicated that nanoparticles consisted of magnetite and maghemite, and no oxyhydroxide species were detected” (Chourpa et al.). To obtain the relative spectral contribution of maghemite and magnetite, a deconvolution with Lorentzian profiles was made.

The Raman spectra had been made by a laser excitation at 632.8 nm. “Laser power delivered by the laser (15 mW) was reduced via filters (optical densities 0.3, 0.6, 1, 2, 3 and 4).” A laser power at the sample of 0.4 mW was avoiding the sample degradation (Chourpa et al.). The required chemistry for the investigation by Chourpa and coworkers is ferric and ferrous chloride and nitrate, potassium dichromate, nitric acid, and others provided by Fluka. “Black iron oxide (iron(II,III)) was supplied by Prolabo (France)”. “Before studying the nanoparticles, [Chourpa and coworkers] analysed bulk samples of commercially purchased black iron oxide ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$)”. The researchers observed that, according to the investigated localization, the Raman spectra “exhibited variable mixtures of two or three oxides”: magnetite, maghemite and hematite. In the Figure 1 by Chourpa et al., we can find the confocal micro-Raman measurements with black iron oxide. The peaks are at (in cm^{-1}):

<i>Bulk magnetite:</i>	194		303		528	662	
<i>Magnetite contaminated:</i>	225	247	292	411	496	662	1318

The magnetite is contaminated with laser-independent hematite (experimental conditions with 0.4 mW of 632.817 nm laser line). The spectra of bulk and contaminated magnetite show the magnetite band at 662 cm^{-1} . “The low-power laser irradiation did not produce any significant variation of hematite/magnetite ratio with time. In contrast, the signal of hematite induced with double the laser power ... was progressively growing over that of magnetite. ... With 1.6 mW and above, the increase of the hematite signal was almost instantaneous and was accompanied by a disappearance of the magnetite band at 662 cm^{-1} . *The resulting hematite bands were broader and shifted to lower frequencies*” (Chourpa et al., 2005). In the Figure 2, we can find the peaks of the Raman spectra of hematite generated by laser power of 0.8 mW and 1.6 mW.

<i>0.8 mW</i>	219	283	397	597	671
<i>1.6 mW</i>	213	271	376	578	

Chourpa and coworkers “aimed to prepare *superparamagnetic nanoparticles free of antiferromagnetic hematite*.” They “did not detect any laser-independent hematite in the samples of synthetically prepared nanoparticles. *Compared to the bulk oxide, the nanoparticles appeared generally somewhat more resistant to hematite formation* upon laser heating: they resisted laser powers of more than 0.4 mW during 1 hour without any spectral change”. The researchers also note that, besides the laser power, an exposure to oxygen “is essential for the formation of hematite.” Chourpa and coworkers suggest also that the observed “laser-stimulated hematite was formed from pre-initialised oxidation sites (domains rich in oxygen and hematite germs)”.

The lacunar phase maghemite is also considered in detail. “The great diversity of spectra reported in the literature illustrates the difficulty in obtaining a representative Raman spectrum of pure maghemite”. The most part of literature shows the maghemite with three broad peaks at around 360–380, 500 and 660–720 cm^{-1} . “In practice, these bands are most often accompanied by bands testifying to the presence of other iron oxide or oxyhydroxide species” (Chourpa et al., 2005). To determine the peaks of maghemite, Chourpa and coworkers opted for nanoparticles. In the Figure 4 and in the Table 1, the Raman spectral data for the CP and OX nanoparticles are available, with assignments.

	<i>magnetite</i>		<i>maghemite</i>		<i>magnetite</i>		<i>maghemite</i>	
<i>CP</i>	195	330	383	496	671	712	1360	
<i>OX</i>	195	330	383	499	671	712	1400	

Nanosizing

In Owens and Orosz, 2006, we can find a study about the “effect of nanosizing on the Raman spectra ... of the hematite phase of Fe₂O₃ produced by laser decomposition of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles”. In the Figure 2 of their article, we can see analyzed the Raman spectra for bulk and nanoparticles of Fe₃O₄ recorded at room temperature. “No frequency shifts or broadening of the Raman lines are observed in the nanoparticles compared to the bulk material”. In particular, the Raman spectra were obtained with a 632 nm 20 mW laser, with density filter D=4. Owens and Orosz concluded that a “9 nm nanosizing is not affecting the vibrational frequencies in the Fe₃O₄ nanoparticle” (see also references therein).

The peaks in their Figure 2 are (in cm⁻¹): 432 495 604 711

Increasing the laser power, the “bulk Fe₃O₄ converts to the hematite phase of Fe₂O₃” (Owens and Orosz, mentioning Shebanova and Lazor). In the Figure 3 by Owens and Orosz we can find the spectra obtained from bulk Fe₃O₄ and nanoparticles of Fe₃O₄, with the same focused laser without the filter. Changing the laser intensity, “new Raman lines have appeared. The frequencies of the new spectra are in good agreement with the frequencies of the previously reported Raman spectra of the Fe₂O₃ hematite phase” (Owens and Orosz are mentioning Hart et al. and Beattie and Gilson).

<i>Bulk</i>	223	288	407	431	493	606	657	711
<i>Nanoparticles</i>	218	280	394	432	495	602		711

Maghemite

Maghemite spectra are proposed by RRUFF for sample R140712, source Rock Currier, owner RRUFF. The sample is a black aggregate of small to fine grains. “The identification of this mineral has been confirmed only by single crystal X-ray diffraction”. Chemistry: (Fe³⁺_{0.67}□_{0.33})Fe³⁺₂O₄, where the □ represents a vacancy. <https://rruff.info/maghemite>

Fig.6a: Maghemite Raman spectra from RRUFF Project website.

Fig.6b: The same as in Fig. 6a in semi logarithmic scale.

Monika Hanesch, using a confocal-Raman spectrometer equipped with a Nd-YAG laser (532.2 nm), studied the maghemite. “The laser power was kept low because 1 mW laser power led to the transformation of the maghemite to haematite and, hence, the measurement of haematite spectra”. In her Figure 7, M. Hanesch is giving maghemite bands identified at 350, 512, 664, 726 and 1330 cm^{-1} . “The bands coincide with those measured by Jacintho et al. (2007)”. And small peaks of haematite can be observed sometimes (224, 294 and 411 cm^{-1}). Let us add data from Chamritski and Burns (2005): 350, 500 and 700 cm^{-1} .

Lepidocrocite in ROD

Fig.7a: Raman spectra of Lepidocrocite from Raman Open Database (ROD). ROD 1000027 (laser 780 nm) data courtesy Wyckoff, 1963, <https://solsa.crystallography.net/rod/1000027.rod> ; ROD 1000195 (laser 532) data courtesy Wyckoff, 1963, <https://solsa.crystallography.net/rod/1000195.rod> ; and ROD 3500284 (laser 633 nm) data courtesy Kumar et al., 2019, <https://solsa.crystallography.net/rod/3500284.rod>

Fig.7b: The same as in Fig.7a with semi log scale.

Here the peaks (in cm^{-1}):

ROD 1000027:	215	247 (strong)	294	302	373 (strong)	518	525	531	538	545	644	659
ROD 1000195:	217	250 (strong)	306	347	380				527 (strong)		650	
ROD 3500284:	217	252 (strong)	310	347	378 (strong)				528 (strong)		650	

Goethite and lepidocrocite ($\alpha\text{-FeOOH}$ and $\gamma\text{-FeOOH}$)

In Thibeu et al., 1978, the Raman spectra of FeO , Fe_3O_4 , $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, $\alpha\text{-FeOOH}$, and $\gamma\text{-FeOOH}$, which are “the common products of iron oxidation”, are given. “Raman spectra of the oxides of iron can be obtained with little difficulty using conventional instrumentation. ... Spectra of thin surface films are identical to those of the pure compounds comprising the films”(Thibeu et al., 1978). Thibeu and coworkers add that it is observed “considerable variation in intensity of Raman scattering from these oxides. The black compounds, FeO and Fe_3O_4 , give weak spectra, whereas those which are lighter in color, $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, $\alpha\text{-FeOOH}$, and $\gamma\text{-FeOOH}$, give stronger spectra”.

The crystalline $\alpha\text{-FeOOH}$ goethite was obtained precipitating by hydrolysis a ferric oxalate solution, with additional adjusting NaHCO_3 solution. The hydrolysis of a ferrous chloride solution is giving $\gamma\text{-FeOOH}$ lepidocrocite. In the Table I by Thibeu et al., we find the spectra.

Goethite:	298	397	414	474	550
Lepidocrocite:	252	380			

The spectra of Goethite and Lepidocrocite are proposed also by Monika Hanesch, 2009.

Goethite :	244	299	385	480	548	681
Lepidocrocite:	250	348	379	528	650	

According to Hanesch, the measured spectrum of synthetic goethite “corresponds to the spectra of this mineral shown in the literature” (M. Hanesch is mentioning Oh et al., 1998). “The combination of a strong peak at 385 cm^{-1} with clear peaks at 244, 299, 480, 548 and 681 cm^{-1} is easy to distinguish from any other spectrum. Synthetic goethite was measured with a laser power of 0.1 mW” (Hanesch, 2009). For the synthetic lepidocrocite too, Hanesch finds the same bands known from literature (Oh et al. 1998). The sample is “stable also at 0.1 mW laser power”.

The shape of the nanoparticles

There is a manner to distinguish goethite nanoparticles, and it is the observation of their shape. Goethite has needle-like or acicular shape particles (pure goethite, needle-like) (Legodi & de Waal, 2007). Magnetite and hematite particles have a pseudocubic shape, according to Legodi and de Wall. However, spherical and rod-like magnetite nanoparticles have been synthesized too (Baghshahi & Yousefi, 2021). In the Fig.8, we are showing the rod-like magnetite nanoparticle, prepared by Cheng et al., according to the method by Fortin et al., 2007. Recently, Fe_3O_4 particles acicular and octahedral structures have been disclosed too (Shu et al., 2021). Even nanotubes - $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@\text{C}$ core-shell nanotubes - have been prepared (Li et al., 2014). For more information about the shapes of particles, see Cornell and Schwertmann, 2003.

As explained by Martina et al., 2022, the goethite nanoparticles are needle-like structures, “naturally asymmetric and anisotropic and with antiferromagnetic properties”. We could tell that these particles are analogous to the rod-like molecules of liquid crystals. “Lemaire et al. widely investigated aqueous suspensions of goethite nanorods giving rise to stable *isotropic and nematic phases* showing peculiar magnetic properties because goethite nanorods align parallel to a weak magnetic field but perpendicular to a strong field” (Martina et al., and references therein).

Fig.8: Spherical and rod-like magnetite nanoparticle. Image courtesy from the article by Cheng, D., Li, X., Zhang, G., & Shi, H. © 2014 licensee Springer. It is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License 4.0, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly credited.

Goethite in RRUFF

In the RRUFF database we can find four goethite samples. <https://rruff.info/goethite>

Here in the following figure, the sample R120086 (chemistry FeO(OH)), source Michael Scott S102426. <https://rruff.info/goethite/R120086> .

Fig. 9: Raman spectra of Goethite sample R120086.

Here the peaks from the Raman spectra in RRUFF, compared with the previously give data (in cm^{-1}):

R050142 (laser 532 nm)	210	225	246-250	302	430	480	550	685	1000	1290
X050091 (laser 785 nm)		224	245	300	348	388	417	437	478	549
X050093 (laser 785 nm)			243	298	347	396	438	478	547	
R120086 (laser 780 nm)166			245	300	386	482	549			
R120086 (laser 532 nm)			246	300	387-400	481	546			
Thibeau et al.:				298	397	414	474	550		
Hanesch:			244	299	385	480	548	681		

For R050142 we used the 0° depolarized signal.

De Faria et al. studies

The article by De Faria et al. starts observing that “understanding of rusting mechanisms is of fundamental importance in corrosion control”. Consequently, “Rust composition has been the subject of several investigations,” to understand the corrosion mechanisms. The main corrosion products are oxides and oxyhydroxides, which are strongly absorbing infrared radiation but are poorly scattering

light. According De Faria et al., this is a possible reason why we have more studies based on IR spectrometry than on Raman spectroscopy. But Raman spectroscopy has advantages over IR spectroscopy (see them illustrated in De Faria and coworkers' article).

In De Faria et al. we can find stressed that the need for Raman "reference spectra for the most common iron oxidation products [was] inspired the work of Thibeau et al.", who proposed spectra of FeO, Fe₃O₄, α-Fe₂O₃, α-FeOOH and γ-FeOOH. In Hart et al. we can find Hematite and Magnetite, with a "precise and complete assignment" for the bands. Beattie and Gibson studied the effects of orientation for single α-Fe₂O₃ crystals. "Raman spectroscopy was also employed by Boucherit et al., Thierry et al., and Nauer et al., who aimed to characterize corrosion processes in iron-water interfaces". Then, we can find mentioned the SERS studies by Oblonsky and Devine. "In these studies, high laser power was employed (from 100 to 500 mW) and this could lead to sample degradation". With the recent Raman instruments, "it is now possible to obtain good quality spectra even from very poor light scatterers using a few hundred micro watts or even less" (De Faria et al.). The existence of disagreements in the Raman spectra of iron oxides and oxyhydroxides available from literature was the stimulus of De Faria and coworkers' research. We can find Raman spectra of hematite, magnetite, wüstite (FeO), maghemite (γ-Fe₂O₃), goethite (α-FeOOH), lepidocrocite (α-FeOOH) and δ-FeOOH. The aim is also that of understanding the influence of laser power.

Hematite

De Faria and coworkers are giving their experimental data in the in Figures 1-3 of their article. Let us consider the data available in their work about Hematite.

Hematite is a crystal with expected seven phonon lines in Raman spectra: two A_{1g} modes (225 and 498 cm⁻¹) and five E_g modes (247, 293, 299, 412 and 613 cm⁻¹). In Hart et al. and R. Beattie and Gilson, the 293 and 299 cm⁻¹ bands were resolved at 100 K or less. In De Faria et al., in the Raman spectrum of hematite at room temperature, the 299 cm⁻¹ band appears as a shoulder of the 293 cm⁻¹ band.

De Faria et al. Raman frequencies of Hematite (in cm⁻¹): 226 245 293 298 413 500 612.

Several samples (natural and synthetic hematite) were studied by De Faria and coworkers, finding similar results, "except for changes in relative intensities that occurred when natural samples" had been considered. The researchers explain that the natural samples are much more crystalline than the synthetic samples. Then, the natural crystals are sensitive to sample orientation. Hematite is antiferromagnetic, with magnons as collective spin movements. The intense band at 1320 cm⁻¹ is "assigned to a two-magnon scattering". "Raising the laser power to 7 mW (at the sample) causes the bands to broaden and to undergo a small shift to lower wavenumbers".

De Faria and coworkers use as Raman equipment a Renishaw Raman imaging microscope (System 3000) and the spectra are excited with an He-Ne laser 632.8 nm radiation. Here the data (in cm⁻¹):

Laser 0.7 mW: 226.7 245.7 292.5 299.3 410.9 497.1 611.9

Laser 7 mW: 219.6 236.5 282.7 295.2 395.9 492.3 596.0

Let us add the data by Murugappan and coworkers, Monika Hanesch, El Mendili et al., Chamritski and Burns, and by Owens and Orosz, for comparison (in cm⁻¹):

<i>Murugappan et al.:</i>	205	268	328	560					
<i>Hanesch:</i>	225	245	290-300	412					
<i>De Faria et al.:</i>	226	245	293 298	413	500	612			
<i>El Mendili et al.</i>	229	248	295	414	502	614		1320	
<i>RRUFF 040024</i>	119	225	246.5	296.5	411	500 558 610.5	655.5	1319	
<i>Chamritski and Burns</i>	225	247	293 299	412	498	613			
<i>Owens and Orosz (bulk)</i>	223		288	407 431	493	606	657	711	
<i>Owens and Orosz (NPs)</i>	218		280	394 432	495	602		711	

Let us remember that data by Owens and Orosz have been obtained from the transition to hematite from magnetite induced by the laser power.

Encapsulation IronOxide@C

We have mentioned before the encapsulation of magnetic nanoparticle. In Song et al., 2012, an approach to an “amorphous carbon coating on the surface” of iron oxide particles, “via a simple glucose treatment” is given. The researchers obtained “novel configurations of iron oxides [which] possess an amorphous carbon layer and ferrous state with high electronic conductivity, which definitely enhances their electrochemical properties compared to pristine iron oxides”.

In the Figure 4 by Song et al., we can find “the Raman spectra of iron oxide and carbon-encapsulated Fe₃O₄ nanocrystals. Iron oxide can normally be categorized as a material for which special care has to be taken during the measurement of Raman spectra because the transition metal (iron) inside its structure is divalent (ferrous or ferric)”. Song and coworkers tell that the Raman spectrum of the pristine iron oxide that they have characterized possesses three broad bands at 390, 590 and 710 cm⁻¹ and two bands around 1360 and 1580 cm⁻¹ attributed to a typical hematite” (Song et al., mentioning Shebanova and Lazor). Song et al. do not provide information about the used Raman equipment and laser power.

Then Song and coworkers continue in the following manner. “Because a laser with even very low energy can evolve numerous spurious peaks attributed to hematite in the Raman spectra of magnetite, the peaks at 300 and 410–420 cm⁻¹ also reported in some previous studies on magnetite are relevant to an oxidation reaction during a Raman experiment”. Song and coworkers are giving details about the magnetite Raman bands, which the authors are indicating in their Figure 4. Using glucose to prepare the nanoparticles, the researchers “figure out that the glucose treatment is definitely *relevant to the phase transition from hematite to magnetite* [Graves et al., Varadwaj et al., 2004]. ... there is a clear change associated with the turnaround of intensity between the D band (1350 cm⁻¹) and the G band (1580 cm⁻¹) after the decomposition of glucose. The augmented D band compared to the G band shows us that *the decomposition of glucose not only activates the phase transition of hematite to magnetite* but also makes the amorphous carbon layer on the surface of the evolved magnetite iron oxide show good agreement with XRD and TEM results” (Song et al., 2012). From hematite to magnetite?

Here the Raman peaks of IronOxide@C (in cm⁻¹):

225 284 334 389 506 582 713 1176 1392 1605

Maghemite NPs capped with polyol

In Varadwaj et al., 2004, we find maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, Bahari, A. (2017). “Among the various magnetic nanomaterials, $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ is used in magnetic memory devices, color imaging, magnetic refrigeration, ferrofluids, catalysis and sensors. Coating or capping the nanoparticles with polymers or organic moieties further enhances their applicability as it prevents agglomeration and the material becomes dispersible in aqueous or organic solvents” (see please Varadwaj et al., and references therein). Varadwaj and coworkers propose $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ “nanoparticles capped with a polyol”, “synthesized by a one-step method”. Stability towards degradation is investigated with Raman laser.

Varadwaj and coworkers used a Renishaw Raman System 1000B and a laser at 514 nm. “Most of the Raman studies on bulk iron oxides have been on Fe_3O_4 and $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ ”. In magnetite we have five Raman bands, but in “earlier studies only four bands at 193, 306, 538 and 668 cm^{-1} are observed” (Varadwaj et al., mentioning Shebanova and Lazor). For $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, seven “phonon lines are expected at 225, 247, 293, 299, 412, 498 and 613 cm^{-1} . In addition to these bands an intense band at 1320 cm^{-1} is observed due to a two magnon scattering”. The $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ has a Raman spectrum characterized by three broad bands around 350, 500 and 700 cm^{-1} , not present in the spectrum of any iron oxide or oxyhydroxide.

Fe_3O_4 @Biochar

In [ChemRxiv](#), January 2023, we considered the literature regarding the use of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles for EMI shielding. From this work we can deduce that, besides the use of encapsulated NPs to have composites, another approach is that of mixing the precursors of magnetic nanoparticles directly in a relevant supporting material. In ChemRxiv, we focused on biochar² as support of NPs. For instance, Li et al., 2016, proposed a Fe_3O_4 @Biochar. The spongy pomelo pericarp is used for biochar, grounded into fine powders. Biochar is mixed with $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (ferric nitrate also known as iron nitrate) in water. After intense stirring, the mixture is desiccated and dried. Put into a tube furnace and heated in flowing N_2 , the final product is denoted as Fe_3O_4 NP/C (see all details in the article by Li et al., 2016, and also how the prepared biochar is acid-treated). In Li et al., 2016, we cannot find Raman spectra.

Raman spectra are given in Nguyen et al., 2020, where the magnetic Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles are decorating biochar obtained from pomelo peel. The researchers prepare different mixtures, one of them is named FO5. Nguyen and coworkers tell that “to confirm the composite formation between Fe_3O_4 and PPB [pomelo peel biochar], Raman spectra was measured at an excitation wavelength of 635 nm using a Renishaw spectrometer. Figure 4(c) [in Nguyen et al.] shows Raman spectra of PPB, Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles, and FO5-PPB before and after adsorption”. No information about the laser power is provided and no mention of the related oxidation problems.

“The whole spectra displayed almost all the peaks that are characteristic to the Fe_3O_4 magnetite structure and graphite of carbon materials. Peaks at lower Raman shift values (218, 276, 393, 687, and 698 cm^{-1}) ... may indicate the vibration modes of Fe–O bonds within each Fe_3O_4 nanoparticle and the Fe–C bonds on the surface of the PPB” (Nguyen et al., mentioning Tiwari et al., 2007 and 2008). As told before, Tiwari and coworkers are not mentioning carbon, therefore they are not mentioning Fe–C at the surface of biochar (see the Appendix about Tiwari et al. works). In any case, here the peaks provided by Nguyen et al. for FO5 (in cm^{-1}):

FO5: 218 276 398 485 594 1298

² Biochar is the black residue, composed of carbon and ashes, obtained after the pyrolysis of biomass. According to the International Biochar Initiative, biochar is “the solid material obtained from the thermochemical conversion of biomass in an oxygen-limited environment”.

In Tiwari et al. works no Fe-C discussion is given because carbon is not investigated. Some information we can find in Chen et al., where a “facile fabrication of 3D biochar absorbers dual-loaded with Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles for enhanced microwave absorption” is proposed. The Raman spectra are given for the Fe₃O₄@SP[spirulina]-BC and SP-BC composites (Fig. 2b [of Chen et al.]). Chen and coworkers are not showing the Raman shift below 300 cm⁻¹. “All the samples exhibited two characteristic peaks at approximately 1340 cm⁻¹ and 1585 cm⁻¹, which represented effective carbonization in the form of D and G bands, respectively” (Chen et al., 2023). “Generally, the ID/IG ratio [I intensity] is commonly utilized to assess the defects and disorder degree in carbonized composites. In this case, the ID/IG value of Fe₃O₄@SP-BCs was higher than that of SP-BC-700, indicating that more defects and disordered carbon components were formed due to the loading of Fe₃O₄ NPs” (Chen et al., 2023).

According to Chen and coworkers, the composite is characterized by a “strong dipole polarization in the biochar matrix under EM waves, which further enhanced the dielectric loss of the absorbers” (Chen et al., and references therein). “The ID/IG ratio increased distinctly as the carbonization temperature increased”, and this “could be attributed to the complete pyrolysis of organic components in the Fe₃O₄@SP precursors” (Chen et al., 2023).

Remarks

It is convenient to use filters to reduce laser power to avoid the sample deterioration.

Time is also important, to understand how sample oxidation is evolving.

Encapsulation seems being important to maintain the superparamagnetic nature of Fe₃O₄.

XRD is distinguishing magnetite and hematite.

Appendix – Magnetic properties of Iron oxides

In Cornell and Schwertmann, 2003, we can find the magnetic structure and the properties of iron oxides. Here we report only the temperatures (T_N = Néel temperature, T_C = Curie temperature, T_M = temperature of Morin transition), and the magnetic structures.

Oxide - Temperature - Magnetic structure

Goethite - 400 T_N -- antiferromagnetic

Lepidocrocite - 77 T_N - antiferromagnetic

Akaganéite - 290 T_N - antiferromagnetic

Delta-FeOOH - 440-460 T_N - ferrimagnetic

Feroxyhyte - 459 T_C - ferrimagnetic

HP FeOOH .. about 350 T_N - antiferromagnetic

Ferrihydrite - about 350 T_N - speromagnetic

Bernalite - about 427 T_N - weakly ferromagnetic

Hematite - 956 T_C - weakly ferromagnetic

Hematite - 260 T_M - antiferromagnetic

Magnetite - 850 T_C (T_N in Kozlenko et al., 2019). - ferrimagnetic

Magnetite - 120 Verwey transition - ferrimagnetic

Maghemite - 820-986 T_C - ferrimagnetic

Epsilon- Fe_2O_3 - 1016 T_N - antiferromagnetic

$Fe(OH)_2$ - 34 T_N - planar antiferromagnetic

Wüstite - 203-211 T_N - antiferromagnetic

About Verwey transition, see:

<https://www.esrf.fr/UsersAndScience/Publications/Highlights/2006/MAT/MAT02>

“Magnetite (Fe_3O_4) is a fascinating natural mineral which is a metallic ferrimagnet at ambient conditions. ... Magnetite has become an important ingredient in the formation of metallic/magnetic nano-composites. In 1939 Verwey discovered a remarkable phenomenon in magnetite, a discontinuous drop in the conductance on cooling the sample below 122 K. This temperature T_V has been nicknamed the Verwey temperature and was shown to be dependent on stoichiometry”.

Appendix - Tiwari et al. studies

Since we have seen the works by Tiwari et al. mentioned in relation with carbon, let us remember the subjects or their articles, to show that carbon does not exist in them.

In “Probing antiphase boundaries in Fe_3O_4 thin films using micro-Raman spectroscopy”, Tiwari and coworkers present a Raman study of magnetite films possessing different thicknesses “grown on single crystal Si and MgO substrates to investigate the presence of antiphase boundaries (APBs). “Raman scattering was performed at room temperature to investigate the effect of substrate and thickness on the vibrational properties. The presence of various modes in Fe_3O_4 can be found in Ref. [Gasparov et al., 2000]. Figure 2 shows the Raman spectra of all the Fe_3O_4 films” (Tiwari et al.).

In the “Oriented growth of Fe_3O_4 thin film on crystalline and amorphous substrates by pulsed laser deposition”, Tiwari and coworkers “have deposited magnetite thin films ... from a $\alpha-Fe_2O_3$ target on different substrates (Si (1 1 1), GaAs (1 0 0), Al_2O_3 (0 0 1) and amorphous float glass (FG)) without any buffer layer at a substrate temperature of 450 °C” (Tiwari et al.).

“The Raman spectra were recorded at room temperature in backscattering configuration using a HR800 Jobin-Yvon spectrometer having a resolution of 1 cm^{-1} . An He-Ne laser (632.8 nm) was used as an excitation source at a power of 9 mW on the sample” (Tiwari et al.).

References

- [1] Aisida, S. O., Akpa, P. A., Ahmad, I., Zhao, T. K., Maaza, M., & Ezema, F. I. (2020). Bio-inspired encapsulation and functionalization of iron oxide nanoparticles for biomedical applications. *European polymer journal*, 122, 109371.
- [2] Avloni, J., Ouyang, M., Florio, L., Henn, A. R., & Sparavigna, A. (2007). Shielding effectiveness evaluation of metallized and polypyrrole-coated fabrics. *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, 20(3), 241-254.
- [3] Baghshahi, S., & Yousefi, F. (2021). A New Systematic Approach to the Morphology and Magnetic Properties of Spherical, Cubic, and Rod-like Magnetite Nanoparticles. *Journal of Superconductivity and Novel Magnetism*, 34, 1949-1954.
- [4] Bahari, A. (2017). Characteristics of Fe_3O_4 , $\alpha-Fe_2O_3$, and $\gamma-Fe_2O_3$ nanoparticles as suitable candidates in the field of nanomedicine. *Journal of Superconductivity and Novel Magnetism*, 30, 2165-2174.

- [5] Beattie, I. R., & Gilson, T. R. (1970). The single-crystal Raman spectra of nearly opaque materials. Iron (III) oxide and chromium (III) oxide. *Journal of the Chemical Society A: Inorganic, Physical, Theoretical*, 980-986.
- [6] Bersani, D., Lottici, P. P., & Montenero, A. (1999). Micro-Raman investigation of iron oxide films and powders produced by sol-gel syntheses. *Journal of Raman spectroscopy*, 30(5), 355-360.
- [7] Blaney, L. (2007). Magnetite (Fe₃O₄): Properties, synthesis, and applications. Lehigh Preserve Collection, Volume 15, Paper 5. <http://preserve.lehigh.edu/cas-lehighreview-vol-15/5>
- [8] Boucherit, N., Hugot-Le Goff, A., & Joiret, S. (1991). Raman studies of corrosion films grown on Fe and Fe-6Mo in pitting conditions. *Corrosion Science*, 32(5-6), 497-507.
- [9] Bruschi, M. L., & de Toledo, L. D. A. S. (2019). Pharmaceutical applications of iron-oxide magnetic nanoparticles. *Magnetochemistry*, 5(3), 50.
- [10] Chamritski, I., & Burns, G. (2005). Infrared-and Raman-active phonons of magnetite, maghemite, and hematite: a computer simulation and spectroscopic study. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 109(11), 4965-4968.
- [11] Chen, T., Cai, J., Gong, D., Liu, C., Liu, P., Cheng, X., & Zhang, D. (2023). Facile fabrication of 3D biochar absorbers dual-loaded with Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles for enhanced microwave absorption. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 935, 168085.
- [12] Cheng, D., Li, X., Zhang, G., & Shi, H. (2014). Morphological effect of oscillating magnetic nanoparticles in killing tumor cells. *Nanoscale research letters*, 9, 1-8.
- [13] Chourpa, I., Douziech-Eyrolles, L., Ngaboni-Okassa, L., Fouquenot, J. F., Cohen-Jonathan, S., Soucé, M., Marchais, H., & Dubois, P. (2005). Molecular composition of iron oxide nanoparticles, precursors for magnetic drug targeting, as characterized by confocal Raman microspectroscopy. *Analyst*, 130(10), 1395-1403.
- [14] Cornell, R. M., & Schwertmann, U. (2003). The iron oxides: structure, properties, reactions, occurrences, and uses (Vol. 664). Weinheim: Wiley-vch.
- [15] De Faria, D. L., Venâncio Silva, S., & De Oliveira, M. T. (1997). Raman microspectroscopy of some iron oxides and oxyhydroxides. *Journal of Raman spectroscopy*, 28(11), 873-878.
- [16] Degiorgi, L., Blatter-Mörke, I., & Wachter, P. (1987). Magnetite: Phonon modes and the Verwey transition. *Physical Review B*, 35(11), 5421.
- [17] Dünnwald, J., & Otto, A. (1989). An investigation of phase transitions in rust layers using Raman spectroscopy. *Corrosion science*, 29(9), 1167-1176.
- [18] El Mendili, Y., Bardeau, J. F., Randrianantoandro, N., Grasset, F., & Greneche, J. M. (2012). Insights into the mechanism related to the phase transition from γ -Fe₂O₃ to α -Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles induced by thermal treatment and laser irradiation. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, 116(44), 23785-23792.
- [19] El Mendili, Y., Vaitkus, A., Merkys, A., Gražulis, S., Chateigner, D., Mathevet, F., Gascoin, S., Petit, S., Bardeau, J.-F., Zanatta, M., Secchi, M., Mariotto, G., Kumar, A., Cassetta, M., Lutterotti, L., Borovin, E., Orberger, B., Simon, P., Hehlen, B., & Le Guen, M. (2019). Raman Open Database: first interconnected Raman-X-ray diffraction open-access resource for material identification. *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, 52(3), 618-625. doi: 10.1107/s1600576719004229
- [20] Fernández-Remolar, D. C. (2015). Iron Oxides, Hydroxides and Oxy-hydroxides. *Encyclopedia of Astrobiology*, 1268-1270. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-44185-5_1714
- [21] Fortin, J. P., Wilhelm, C., Servais, J., Ménager, C., Bacri, J. C., & Gazeau, F. (2007). Size-sorted anionic iron oxide nanomagnets as colloidal mediators for magnetic hyperthermia. *Journal of the american chemical society*, 129(9), 2628-2635.
- [22] Gasparov, L. V., Tanner, D. B., Romero, D. B., Berger, H., Margaritondo, G., & Forro, L. (2000). Infrared and Raman studies of the Verwey transition in magnetite. *Physical Review B*, 62(12), 7939.
- [23] Graves, P. R., Johnston, C., & Campaniello, J. J. (1988). Raman scattering in spinel structure ferrites. *Materials Research Bulletin*, 23(11), 1651-1660.
- [24] Gupta, R., Sood, A. K., Metcalf, P., & Honig, J. M. (2002). Raman study of stoichiometric and Zn-doped Fe₃O₄. *Physical Review B*, 65(10), 104430.

- [25] Hai, N. H., Phu, N. D., Luong, N. H., Chau, N., Chinh, H. D., Hoang, L. H., & Leslie-Pelecky, D. L. (2008). Mechanism for sustainable magnetic nanoparticles under ambient conditions. *Journal -Korean Physical Society*, 52(5), 1327.
- [26] Hanesch, M. (2009). Raman spectroscopy of iron oxides and (oxy) hydroxides at low laser power and possible applications in environmental magnetic studies. *Geophysical Journal International*, 177(3), 941-948.
- [27] Hart, T.R., Adams, S.B., Temkin, H. (1976). In: M. Balkanski, R. Leite, S. Porto (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Light Scattering in Solids*, Flammarion, Paris, 1976, pp. 254–258.
- [28] Hou, Y., Yu, J., & Gao, S. (2003). Solvothermal reduction synthesis and characterization of superparamagnetic magnetite nanoparticles. *Journal of Materials Chemistry*, 13(8), 1983-1987.
- [29] Jacintho, G. V., Corio, P., & Rubim, J. C. (2007). Surface-enhanced Raman spectra of magnetic nanoparticles adsorbed on a silver electrode. *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry*, 603(1), 27-34.
- [30] Kiely, C. H. (2006). *Materials for nanotechnology notes*.
- [31] Kozlenko, D. P., Dubrovinsky, L. S., Kichanov, S. E., Lukin, E. V., Cerantola, V., Chumakov, A. I., & Savenko, B. N. (2019). Magnetic and electronic properties of magnetite across the high pressure anomaly. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 4464.
- [32] Kumar, P., Tomar, V., Kumar, D., Joshi, R. K., & Nemiwal, M. (2022). Magnetically active iron oxide nanoparticles for catalysis of organic transformations: A review. *Tetrahedron*, 106, 132641.
- [33] Kumar, A., Zanatta, M., Bersani, D., Daldosso, N., & Mariotto, G. (2019). Raman spectrum of Fe₃O₄. Personal communication to ROD, 2019
- [34] Kumar, A.; Zanatta, M.; Bersani, D; Daldosso, N.; Mariotto, G. Raman spectrum of FeHO₂. Personal communication to ROD, 2019
- [35] Lafuente, B., Downs, R. T., Yang, H., & Stone, N. (2015). 1. The power of databases: The RRUFF project. In *Highlights in mineralogical crystallography* (pp. 1-30). De Gruyter (O).
- [36] Lee, J. B., Kim, H. J., Lužnik, J., Jelen, A., Pajić, D., Wencka, M., Jagličić, Z., Meden, A., & Dolinšek, J. (2014). Synthesis and magnetic properties of hematite particles in a "nanomedusa" morphology. *Journal of Nanomaterials*, 2014, 191-191.
- [37] Legodi, M. A., & de Waal, D. (2007). The preparation of magnetite, goethite, hematite and maghemite of pigment quality from mill scale iron waste. *Dyes and pigments*, 74(1), 161-168.
- [38] Lemaire, B. J., Davidson, P., Ferré, J., Jamet, J. P., Petermann, D., Panine, P., Dozov, I., Stoenescu, D., & Jolivet, J. P. (2005). The complex phase behaviour of suspensions of goethite (α -FeOOH) nanorods in a magnetic field. *Faraday discussions*, 128, 271-283.
- [39] Lemaire, B. J., Davidson, P., Petermann, D., Panine, P., Dozov, I., Stoenescu, D., & Jolivet, J. P. (2004). Physical properties of aqueous suspensions of goethite (α -FeOOH) nanorods: Part II: In the nematic phase. *The European Physical Journal E*, 13(3), 309-319.
- [40] Li, J. M., Huan, A. C. H., Wang, L., Du, Y. W., & Feng, D. (2000). Interface effects on magnetoresistance and magnetic-field-reduced Raman scattering in magnetite. *Physical Review B*, 61(10), 6876.
- [41] Li, W., Lv, B., Wang, L., Li, G., & Xu, Y. (2014). Fabrication of Fe₃O₄@C core-shell nanotubes and their application as a lightweight microwave absorbent. *RSC Advances*, 4(99), 55738-55744.
- [42] Li, T., Bai, X., Qi, Y. X., Lun, N., & Bai, Y. J. (2016). Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles decorated on the biochar derived from pomelo pericarp as excellent anode materials for Li-ion batteries. *Electrochimica Acta*, 222, 1562-1568.
- [43] Martina, M. R., Zoli, L., & Sani, E. (2022). Synthesis and characterization of goethite (α -FeOOH) magnetic nanofluids. *International Journal of Thermofluids*, 15, 100169.
- [44] Mishra, A. K., & Ramaprabhu, S. (2011). Nano magnetite decorated multiwalled carbon nanotubes: a robust nanomaterial for enhanced carbon dioxide adsorption. *Energy & Environmental Science*, 4(3), 889-895.
- [45] Mohammed, S., Elnoor, M., & Hamad, I. (2018). The Structural Properties of Iron Oxides using Raman Spectroscopy. *J. Sci. Eng. Res.*, 5, 183-187.

- [46] Murugappan, K., Silvester, D. S., Chaudhary, D., & Arrigan, D. W. (2014). Electrochemical Characterization of an Oleyl-coated Magnetite Nanoparticle-Modified Electrode. *ChemElectroChem*, 1(7), 1211-1218.
- [47] Nauer, G., Strecha, P., Brinda-Konopik, N., & Liptay, G. (1985). Spectroscopic and thermoanalytical characterization of standard substances for the identification of reaction products on iron electrodes. *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, 30(4), 813-830.
- [48] Nguyen, V. H., Van, H. T., Nguyen, V. Q., Dam, X. V., Hoang, L. P., & Ha, L. T. (2020). Magnetic Fe₃O₄ nanoparticle biochar derived from pomelo peel for reactive Red 21 adsorption from aqueous solution. *Journal of chemistry*, 2020, 1-14.
- [49] Nguyen, M. D., Tran, H. V., Xu, S., & Lee, T. R. (2021). Fe₃O₄ Nanoparticles: Structures, synthesis, magnetic properties, surface functionalization, and emerging applications. *Applied Sciences*, 11(23), 11301.
- [50] Oblonsky, L. J., & Devine, T. M. (1995). A surface enhanced Raman spectroscopic study of the passive films formed in borate buffer on iron, nickel, chromium and stainless steel. *Corrosion Science*, 37(1), 17-41.
- [51] Oh, S. J., Cook, D. C., & Townsend, H. E. (1998). Characterization of iron oxides commonly formed as corrosion products on steel. *Hyperfine interactions*, 112(1-4), 59-66.
- [52] Ohtsuka, T., Kubo, K., & Sato, N. (1986). Raman spectroscopy of thin corrosion films on iron at 100 to 150 C in air. *Corrosion*, 42(8), 476-481.
- [53] Owens, F. J., & Orosz, J. (2006). Effect of nanosizing on lattice and magnon modes of hematite. *Solid state communications*, 138(2), 95-98.
- [54] Panta, P. C., & Bergmann, C. P. (2015). Raman spectroscopy of iron oxide of nanoparticles (Fe₃O₄). *J. Mater. Sci. Eng*, 5(3).
- [55] Pereira, M. C., Oliveira, L. C. A., & Murad, E. (2012). Iron oxide catalysts: Fenton and Fentonlike reactions—a review. *Clay minerals*, 47(3), 285-302.
- [56] Pouran, S. R., Raman, A. A. A., & Daud, W. M. A. W. (2014). Review on the application of modified iron oxides as heterogeneous catalysts in Fenton reactions. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 64, 24-35.
- [57] Shebanova, O. N., & Lazor, P. (2003). Raman study of magnetite (Fe₃O₄): laser-induced thermal effects and oxidation. *Journal of Raman spectroscopy*, 34(11), 845-852.
- [58] Shebanova, O. N., & Lazor, P. (2003). Raman spectroscopic study of magnetite (Fe₃O₄): a new assignment for the vibrational spectrum. *Journal of Solid State Chemistry*, 174(2), 424-430.
- [59] Slavov, L., Abrashev, M. V., Merodiiska, T., Gelev, C., Vandenberghe, R. E., Markova-Deneva, I., & Nedkov, I. (2010). Raman spectroscopy investigation of magnetite nanoparticles in ferrofluids. *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, 322(14), 1904-1911.
- [60] Song, K., Lee, Y., Jo, M. R., Nam, K. M., & Kang, Y. M. (2012). Comprehensive design of carbon-encapsulated Fe₃O₄ nanocrystals and their lithium storage properties. *Nanotechnology*, 23(50), 505401.
- [61] Sparavigna A. C. (2023). Iron Oxide Fe₃O₄ Nanoparticles for Electromagnetic Shielding. *ChemRxiv*. Cambridge: Cambridge Open Engage; 2023. <https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv-2023-g9bkz-v2>
- [62] Sparavigna, A. C. (2023). Iron Oxide Fe₃O₄ Nanoparticles with Intrinsic Conducting Polymers and Biochar to Improve the Electromagnetic Shielding Performance of Light Weight Absorption-Type Materials. *International Journal of Sciences*, 12(08), 5–23. <https://doi.org/10.18483/ijsci.2709>
- [63] Sparavigna, A. C. (2023). q-Gaussian Tsallis Line Shapes and Raman Spectral Bands. *International Journal of Sciences*, 12(03), 27-40. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18483/ijSci.2671>
- [64] Sparavigna, A. C. (2023). q-Gaussian Tsallis Functions and Egelstaff-Schofield Spectral Line Shapes. *International Journal of Sciences*, 12(03), 47-50. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18483/ijSci.2673>
- [65] Sparavigna, A. C. (2023). q-Gaussian Tsallis Line Shapes for Raman Spectroscopy (June 7, 2023). *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4445044>
- [66] Sparavigna, A. C. (2023). Formamide Raman Spectrum and q-Gaussian Tsallis Lines (June 12, 2023). *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4451881>
- [67] Sparavigna A. C. (2023). Tsallis q-Gaussian function as fitting lineshape for Graphite Raman bands. *ChemRxiv*. Cambridge: Cambridge Open Engage, <https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv-2023-bwnmw>

- [68] Sparavigna A. C. (2003). Fitting q-Gaussians onto Anatase TiO₂ Raman Bands. ChemRxiv. Cambridge: Cambridge Open Engage, <https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv-2023-11vqb>
- [69] Sparavigna, A. (2023). Q-Gaussians and the SERS Spectral Bands of L-Cysteine and Cysteamine. ChemRxiv. Cambridge: Cambridge Open Engage, <https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv-2023-9swp9-v2>
- [70] Thibeau, R. J., Brown, C. W., & Heidersbach, R. H. (1978). Raman spectra of possible corrosion products of iron. *Applied spectroscopy*, 32(6), 532-535.
- [71] Thierry, D., Persson, D., Leygraf, C., Boucherit, N., & Hugot-Le Goff, A. (1991). Raman spectroscopy and XPS investigations of anodic corrosion films formed on FeMo alloys in alkaline solutions. *Corrosion Science*, 32(3), 273-284.
- [72] Tiwari, S., Prakash, R., Choudhary, R. J., & Phase, D. M. (2007). Oriented growth of Fe₃O₄ thin film on crystalline and amorphous substrates by pulsed laser deposition. *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, 40(16), 4943.
- [73] Tiwari, S., Phase, D. M., & Choudhary, R. J. (2008). Probing antiphase boundaries in Fe₃O₄ thin films using micro-Raman spectroscopy. *Applied Physics Letters*, 93(23).
- [74] Tong, S., Zhu, H., & Bao, G. (2019). Magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles for disease detection and therapy. *Materials Today*, 31, 86-99.
- [75] Varadwaj, K. S. K., Panigrahi, M. K., & Ghose, J. (2004). Effect of capping and particle size on Raman laser-induced degradation of γ -Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles. *Journal of Solid State Chemistry*, 177(11), 4286-4292.
- [76] Venkateswarlu, S., Kumar, B. N., Prasad, C. H., Venkateswarlu, P., & Jyothi, N. V. V. (2014). Bio-inspired green synthesis of Fe₃O₄ spherical magnetic nanoparticles using *Syzygium cumini* seed extract. *Physica B: Condensed Matter*, 449, 67-71.
- [77] Verble, J. L. (1974). Temperature-dependent light-scattering studies of the Verwey transition and electronic disorder in magnetite. *Physical Review B*, 9(12), 5236.
- [78] Verwey, E. (1939). Electronic conduction of magnetite (Fe₃O₄) and its transition point at low temperatures. *Nature*, 144(3642), 327-328.
- [79] Wallyn, J., Anton, N., & Vandamme, T. F. (2019). Synthesis, principles, and properties of magnetite nanoparticles for in vivo imaging applications—A review. *Pharmaceutics*, 11(11), 601.
- [80] Wu, W., Wu, Z., Yu, T., Jiang, C., & Kim, W. S. (2015). Recent progress on magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles: synthesis, surface functional strategies and biomedical applications. *Science and technology of advanced materials*, 16(2), 023501.
- [81] Wyckoff, R. W. G. (1963). Second edition. *Crystal Structures*, 1963, 1, 290-295, Interscience Publishers, New York
- [82] Yew, Y. P., Shameli, K., Miyake, M., Khairudin, N. B. B. A., Mohamad, S. E. B., Hara, H., Bt Mad Nordin, M.F., & Lee, K. X. (2017). An eco-friendly means of biosynthesis of superparamagnetic magnetite nanoparticles via marine polymer. *IEEE Transactions on Nanotechnology*, 16(6), 1047-1052.
- [83] Yuvakkumar, R., & Hong, S. I. (2014). Green synthesis of spinel magnetite iron oxide nanoparticles. *Advanced Materials Research*, 1051, 39-42.